
607457-CREA-1-2019-1-ES-CULT-COOP2

Local placemaking activities 2022-2023

Deliverables 4.1 and 4.2

CREATIVE EUROPE Cooperation Project Agreement number 607457-CREA-1-2019-1-ES-CULT-COOP2

The European Commission's support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

A-Place

Deliverables 4.1 and 4.2

Local placemaking activities (2022-2023)

Version 1.0

Editors:

Leandro Madrazo

Petra Pferdmenges

Contributors:

Veronika Antoniou

Luisa Bravo

Leandro Madrazo

Rosaura Romero

Teresa Tourvas

November 30, 2023

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	2
1. Introduction	3
1. A Weaved Place in L'Hospitalet (Barcelona).....	4
2. A Resilient Place in Bologna.....	20
3. A Just Radio in Brussels.....	27
4. AGORA - APlace4All	31
Conclusions.....	35

Executive Summary

This report summarizes the local placemaking activities carried out by partners during the fourth and last year of the A-Place project. The collaborative activities in the last year of the project have concentrated on the closing events and final exhibition (see [Deliverable 3.7](#)) and in the production of a book that includes the most representative work carried out during the four-year project.

The local activities carried out in the last year are of two kinds:

- conclusion of on-going activities initiated in the third year: "A Weaved Place", in L'Hospitalet; "A Resilient Place" in Bologna, and "A Just Radio", in Brussels
- activities initiated in the fourth year: "AGORA: A Spot Place", in Nicosia.

The conclusion includes a reflection on the work done this year, and about the development of the local placemaking activities throughout the four-year project.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and target group

The purpose and target groups of this report are twofold: for partner organizations, its goal is to provide an account of the work conducted in the last year of the project. For external audiences, this compilation offers an overview of a rich variety of placemaking activities carried out by partners in multiple locations and contexts, including their processes and outputs. The conclusion section encompasses a reflection of the work accomplished in the four years of the project, as reported in the previous editions of this deliverable.

1.2 Contribution of partners

Each partner responsible for the placemaking activity has provided a report included in the corresponding chapter. Petra Pferdmenges, from Alive Architecture, has been responsible for collecting the outputs; Leandro Madrazo, project coordinator, has undertaken the editing of the document, including writing the conclusions.

1.3 Relations to other activities in the project

A concise account of each placemaking activity included in this document is available on the project [website](#). The communication work related to the implementation the placemaking activities is detailed in Deliverable 3.2-3-4 "Communication activities 2022-23". The systematic collection and subsequent reflection on the collective work, as outlined in Deliverables 4.1-2 "Local placemaking activities" produced throughout the project, has served as the starting point for further reflections about place and placemaking. These reflexions continued in academic contexts, with the publication of papers and articles, and in a book that summarizes the collective work carried out throughout the project's lifetime.

1. A Weaved Place in L'Hospitalet (Barcelona)

Leandro Madrazo, Ángel Martín, Mario Hernández, Adrià S. Llorens

School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona

1.1 Context

The activities of "A Weaved Place" started in October 2019 and have continued during the whole project duration. In the fourth and last year we have been able to benefit from the work carried out in the previous years, particularly from the ties with the local actors: municipality, schools, and artists. The previous collaborations in various contexts during the last three years gave rise to a complicity and mutual trust which has enabled us to conclude the program of activities with two special events: the ES_CULTURA festival in November 2022, and the closing event in Can Trinxet, on May 2023 (see [Deliverable 3.7](#)).

1.2 Activities

In the academic year 2022-23, the following courses at La Salle School of Architecture have planned their activities within the framework of A-Place:

- **ES_CULTURA Public Art Festival.** On 26 and 27 November 2022, the two-day festival [ES_CULTURA](#) was organized in the Plaça de la Cultura in the Bellvitge neighbourhood in L'Hospitalet, with the support of the municipality and local organizations. Prior to the festival, there was an open call for proposals for artistic interventions in the public space. Ten proposals were selected and built as part of the festival.

- **Mapping and constructing places.** Students of an elective seminar carried out from February to May 2023 were involved in the closing event programme carried out in Can Trinxet, in June 2023. They were assigned the task to analyse the work done by partners in the local activities carried out during the project, summarize them and establish connections between them. The final assignment was to make a proposal to revitalize the old factory of Can Trinxet. The proposals were part of the closing programme.

1.2.1 ES_CULTURA Public Art Festival

TYPE:	Learn-Place, Spot-Place
WHERE:	Plaça de la Cultura, L'Hospitalet
WHEN:	26-27 November 2022
WHO:	Students and faculty from La Salle Architecture Schools; pupils and teachers from local schools; local artists; neighbours' associations
COMMUNICATION:	Open call for interventions in the public space; local media channels; social media channels

The initiative to organize the ES_CULTURA festival originated from the School of Architecture La Salle. The concept of the festival emerged from [previous installations](#) created by architecture students from La Salle and secondary school pupils in the Bellvitge neighbourhood in November 2021. For this festival, we launched an [open call](#) (Figure 1.1) to invite primary and secondary schools' students, university students and artists to submit proposals on the following topics:

- **Memories.** Conveying and sharing personal stories and experiences linked to public spaces; memories and stories that can be shared with the community.
- **Talking objects.** Transforming street furniture into objects that convey messages and ideas.
- **Empty spaces.** Identifying spaces that go unnoticed and giving them new meaning.
- **Agora.** Propose topics for debate on social and cultural issues that affect community life and the use of public space (climate change, social isolation, multiculturalism, etc.).

Figure 1.1. Open call for proposals for the ES_CULTURA festival

A jury, composed by an artist, a representative from the municipal culture department, and A-Place partners, [awarded 10 prizes](#) for the best contribution, including photographs, objects, film screening, and soundscapes. This winning works were then curated for presentation at the festival.

The festival programme was promoted through posters placed on buildings in the neighbourhood (Figure 1.2). To enhance the event engagement and appeal to the local community, we incorporated additional activities, including a drawing and painting workshop for children (Figure 1.3), musical performances and dances by local artists and a senior association (Figure 1.4), as well as opportunities for food and drinks.

A-Place
Linking places through networked artistic practices

26-27 nov. 2022
Plaza de la Cultura

L'Hospitalet de Llobregat

ES CULTURA

Festival de arte público en la Plaza de la Cultura

Sábado 26 de noviembre

10:00-14:00
Instalaciones artísticas seleccionadas en el concurso ES CULTURA

Taller artístico «Imagina tu parque»
Para niños de entre 6 y 12 años.
Organizado por Escuela PlayART.

10:30-11:15
Exhibición de baile en línea
Asociación de Gent Gran de Ca n'Arús.
Acompañamiento al piano y voz de Sílvia Bas. Tras la exhibición, baile popular.

11:30-13:00
Desayuno popular
Acompañamiento en directo con voz de Sílvia Bas.

18:00-19:30
Cine a la fresca
Proyecciones «Cine Club Hospitalet REVIVAL: 20 años después».
Ciclo Hospitalet desde el Documental.
Evento público, gratuito y sin limitación de aforo.

Domingo 27 de noviembre

10:00-14:00
Votación popular de las instalaciones artísticas seleccionadas en el concurso ES CULTURA

Taller artístico «Imagina tu parque»
Para niños de entre 6 y 12 años.
Organizado por Escuela PlayART.

10:30
Apertura por el coro del Casal de Gent Grant de Bellvitge

11:00
Zumba y desayuno popular

18:00-19:30
Cine a la fresca
Proyecciones «Cine Club Hospitalet REVIVAL: 20 años después».
Ciclo Hospitalet desde la Ficción.
Evento público, gratuito y sin limitación de aforo.

Más información sobre el festival:

Co-funded by the Creative Europe Programme of the European Union
Creative Europe Operational Program Agreement
Number 2018-1-CE-IA-1-2018-1-05-001-00092

laSalle

Ajuntament de L'Hospitalet

Figure 1.2. Poster of the festival programme

Figure 1.3. Painting and drawing workshop for children organized by PlayART

Figure 1.4. Dancing performance by seniors' association Ca n'Arús

The winners of the categories schools and universities assembled their installations on the site on Saturday morning and dismantled them on Sunday evening (Figures 1.5-1.10). The works created by students of the School of Architecture La Salle were installed on campus and remained on display for the rest of the semester.

Figure 1.5. "The value of Bellvitge", by students from Institut Bellvitge (winner of an audience award)

Figure 1.6. "Fill the void", by Anna Trasserra, student at the School of Architecture La Salle

Figure 1.7. "Conversing housing", by Dali Salamova, student at the School of Architecture La Salle

Figure 1.8. "Folded", by Darío Bertoli, student at the School of Architecture La Salle

Figure 1.9. "Bureau", by Nerea Mejías, Inés Moxo, Maria Rosa Gavin, Paula Díaz, students at the School of Architecture La Salle (audience award)

Figure 1.10. "Shinrin-Yoku", by Barbora Otáhalová, Marc Salvador, Miranda Villanueva, Sonya Nacheva, students at the School of Architecture La Salle

The two works selected in the artist's category artists were the sound installation "Listening lines" (Figures 1.11, 1.12) and the open-air cinema "Revival" (Figures 1.13-1.15). The latter included an exhibition of posters from old films related to the history of the neighbourhood, as well as evening film projections in the square.

Figures 1.11, 1.12. "Listening lines", by Jimmy Solórzano y Alejandro Artigas

Figure 1.13. "Revival", by Laura Garcimartín. Film posters on the entry to the underground parking at the square (audience award)

Figures 1.14, 1.15. "Revival", views of the historic film posters

Those who visited the event could also vote for their favourite installation (Figures 1.16 and 1.17). We collected 168 votes in the ballot box located at the square.

Figures 1.16 and 1.17. Visitors selected their favourite installation

The audience awards for each of the categories were: “The value of Bellvitge” (Figure 1.5), by students of the Institut Bellvitge, in the category schools; “Bureau” (Figure 1.9), by Nerea Mejías, Inés Moxo, María Rosa Gavin and Paula Díaz, in the category universities; and “Revival” (Figures 1.13-1.15), by Laura Garcimartín in the artists category.

A video reportage of the event was produced and disseminated through A-Place channels. In addition, the festival was disseminated by the local press and television (Figures 1.18, 1.19).

More information:

<https://www.a-place.eu/en/placemaking-action/127>

<https://www.a-place.eu/en/placemaking-action/134>

Figure 1.18. News about the festival on the local television

Figure 1.19. An article in the local press dedicated to the festival

1.2.2 Mapping and constructing places

TYPE:	Learn-Place, Spot-Place
WHERE:	School of Architecture La Salle, City of L’Hospitalet
WHEN:	February -May 2023
WHO:	Students and teachers from elective seminar; pupils from local schools; neighbours associations
COMMUNICATION:	Students’ proposals to activate the spaces of the old factory Can Trinxet were presented in the project closing event

The theme of the elective seminar “Research Seminar of Contemporary Habitat” 2022-23 was the activation of the old Can Trinxet factory in L’Hospitalet as a communal space to celebrate the memory of the place and to open it to new significations. Twenty-two students from diverse nationalities participated in the learning activities integrated with the A-Place project.

Initially, students were introduced to the fundamental concepts of place and placemaking. Then, they focused on studying the city of L’Hospitalet from social, historical and urban perspectives. In parallel, they examined the placemaking activities carried out in the A-Place project using the resources available in the website (reports, videos). Working in teams, they summarized their findings using a template based on the posters of the A-Place final exhibition (Figure 1.20).

Figure 1.20. Template used in the posters of the A-Place final exhibition

The posters were on display at the design studio of the School of Architecture La Salle (Figure 1.21). Students discussed the connections between the various activities carried out by A-Place partners and draw conclusions about placemaking strategies and tools.

Figure 1.21. Panel exhibition and group discussion

The final activity was associated with the closing event organized at Can Trinxet in June 2023. The students' task was to propose interventions in the old factory that would enhance the bonds between the neighbours and the place (Figures 1.22-23).

Huerto Urbano Can Trinxet

Los huertos urbanos son espacios utilizados generalmente por las personas que viven en un barrio para poder convivir al aire libre y a su vez cumplen la función de poder ser utilizados como un espacio para cultivar verduras, hortalizas, frutas, legumbres, plantas aromáticas o hierbas medicinales, para uso doméstico.

Beneficios

Reactiva el uso de la plaza entre los edificios, genera actividad de producción sustentable para los vecinos, reduce el uso de productos químicos, ayuda a fortalecer la seguridad alimentaria, el medio ambiente y la salud. Todo esto generando convivencia, colaboración, integración entre las partes involucradas mientras embellece y hace una conexión entre los edificios existentes.

Propuesta

Se plantea un huerto urbano en el espacio público actualmente vacío entre edificios para que funcione como plaza central. Esto para mejorar la relación interior-exterior con vistas agradables hacia el patio.

A-Place

Cruz Roja - Ajuntament de L'Hospitalet
 Combina las funciones productivas asociadas al autocuidado con finalidades sociales, terapéuticas, educativas y ambientales. Proyecto pionero en Cataluña por su vertiente de favorecer la interrelación social entre los diferentes colectivos que participan. Los terrenos se encuentran en la carretera de Espulgues, entre los barrios de Can Serra y Sanfeliu. Voluntarios y técnicos de la Cruz Roja ofrecen información y asesoramiento sobre técnicas de cultivo y mantenimiento del terreno. También colabora el servicio técnico del Área de Espacio Público, Urbanismo y Sostenibilidad del Ayuntamiento.

Signature of the Past *"Firma del Pasado"*

"Firma del Pasado" tiene como objetivo crear una actividad comunitaria que recuerde a las personas el razonamiento histórico detrás de Can Trinxet. Las cortinas que cuelgan de la rejilla crean áreas semi-visibles en el medio de la fábrica. Esto divide el área en tres, de las dos áreas restantes se reflejan imágenes de estilo antiguo de la fábrica. Dado que las paredes de tela van trasladando imágenes a las demás capas, con el contraste que crean las personas que pasan y bailan podemos ver la interacción entre la gente de hoy con la firma del pasado.

La construcción de esta solución artística es realmente fácil. Mediante la creación de un sistema de rejilla ligera de 3 metros a 3 metros podemos lograr un espacio funcional. Este espacio se puede utilizar de muchas maneras quitando persianas en cada línea de la cuadrícula. Un espacio de 3x3 puede ser de día, de noche... Las cortinas crean un ritmo con la circulación de las personas adentro. Por lo tanto, las personas que visitan el espacio son parte de esta instalación. Las máquinas de proyección a cada lado de la instalación también se reflejan en el medio para crear variedad y accesibilidad a las imágenes de la fábrica mostrada. La idea de esta instalación es crear una imagen de la gente de hoy usando la fábrica del pasado.

Utilizando las persianas como elemento principal en una fábrica de tejidos, proponemos una intervención creativa para memorizar Can Trinxet y resaltar la importancia de la fábrica.

A-Place

Figures 1.22. Students' proposal to activate Can Trinxet

Figures 1.23. Students' proposal to activate Can Trinxet

The proposals were presented in a section of the closing programme (see Deliverable 3.7). Members of the association "Som Santa Eulàlia" were invited to attend the presentation of the proposals (Figures 1.24-1.25). During their comments, the neighbours shared their memories of the place with students and explained their efforts in recent years to preserve the structure as community space, celebrating the long industrial tradition and the fights of the workers for their rights. They emphasized the importance of keeping these memories alive.

Figures 1.24-1.25. Presentation of student's proposals at the closing event in Can Trinxet

1.3 Reflections

In the fourth year, we capitalized on the extensive network of contacts established in the previous three years of the project. This enabled us to expand the reach and impact of our placemaking activities. Both the ES_CULTURA festival and the closing event at Can Trinxet serve as prime examples of placemaking as an ongoing process that necessitates sustained engagement with community stakeholders. This entails understanding their concerns and collaboratively participating in actions that hold significance for all parties involved both the community and academia.

From an academic standpoint, by intertwining learning activities with community-based initiatives, we have successfully solidified an educational approach initiated in earlier years at the School of Architecture La Salle. Through this pedagogic work, we explored methods and strategies to integrate architectural education within the community, overcoming boundaries between academia and society. The activities undertaken throughout the four years of the A-Place project have paved the way for new avenues, allowing us to further progress along this educational path.

2. A Resilient Place in Bologna

Luisa Bravo

City Space Architecture

2.1 Context

"A Resilient Place" is a placemaking activity taking place in the Porto-Saragozza neighbourhood in Bologna, in front of the City Space Architecture (CSA) headquarters. It started in April 2022 ([see Deliverable 4.1-2 "Local placemaking activities 2021-22"](#)) and was intended to transform a small green spot, a left-over space, into a public biodiversity garden.

This green spot is located at the opposite side of the area along via Curiel where City Space Architecture implemented the parklet as a placemaking activity of "["A Visionary Place"](#)" in 2020-21.

After several months of discussions with public officers from the municipality, in October 2022 we signed a Collaboration Pact with the municipality of Bologna, under the framework of "Regulation on Collaboration between Citizens and the City for the Care and Regeneration of Urban Commons", an innovative tool (adopted in 2014) for active engagement of local stakeholders and citizens in the co-creation and management of shared, civic spaces for public use.

In 2023 we implemented the green infrastructure (phase 1 with Fondazione BioHabitat and Linea Verde, phase 2 with Vivai Bergonzini) and organized three major art and creative events intended to activate the garden and engage residents and stakeholders.

2.2 Activities

"A Resilient Place" was conceived as an opportunity to develop community engagement, through physical interaction, especially following the extended period of isolation and confinement during the COVID-19 pandemic. Since November 2022, we worked with Fondazione BioHabitat and Linea Verde for the renovation of the green infrastructure, through a cooperation agreement. However, given the rainy season, that lasted until March 2023, the implementation required more than expected.

Before initiating the implementation of the green infrastructure, we sent an email to the residents along via Curiel, in collaboration of the building managers. Surprisingly, some residents expressed complaints and rejected the proposal, particularly regarding the installation of benches. Concerns were raised about the garden potentially attracting unwanted users and disturbing the tranquillity of the area. Subsequently, we met with residents and engaged in discussions with building managers and the municipality to clarify the placemaking action and the expected impact. Unfortunately, this also resulted in a delay in the implementation.

2.2.1 Implementation of the green infrastructure

TYPE:	Spot place
WHERE:	Onsite - at the green post
WHEN:	November 2022 - July 2023
WHO:	Phase 1 with Fondazione BioHabitat and Linea Verde / Phase 2 with Vivai Bergonzini
COMMUNICATION:	emails, telephone

The renovation of the green infrastructure, as outlined in the cooperation pact, aimed to comprehensively redesign the green space. The municipality requested the preservation and pruning of existing trees where necessary, and the reorganization of the space according to the approved design proposal. Unfortunately, heavy rains persisted until March 2023, In May and June, Bologna and the Emilia Romagna region faced severe flooding, necessitating emergency measures and temporarily halting all ongoing activities.

This unexpected situation prompted Fondazione BioHabitat and Linea Verde to withdraw from the management of the garden, as previously agreed. In June 2023, CSA started a collaboration with Vivai Bergonzini, a landscape gardening firm, to develop a design proposal that could encompass different species and address the biodiversity aspect of the project. The municipality accepted the proposal, and it was subsequently implemented (Figures 2.1-2.4).

Figure 2.1 Design plan of the green infrastructure developed by Vivai Bergonzini, submitted to the municipality of Bologna

Figure 2.2 3D landscape simulation of the green infrastructure developed by Vivai Bergonzini, submitted to the municipality of Bologna

Figure 2.3. The biodiversity public garden completed in July 2023

Figure 2.4 A detail of the green species of the biodiversity public garden

2.2.2 Art event on the occasion of the Art City White Night

TYPE:	Spot-Place
WHERE:	Onsite - at the biodiversity public garden
WHEN:	4 February 2023
WHO:	Italian artist Yari Miele and curator Marcello Tedesco
COMMUNICATION:	emails, telephone, newsletters, social media

The Italian artist Yari Miele created a site-specific installation at CSA headquarters and the biodiversity public garden for the Art City White Night of Arte Fiera (Figures 2.5, 2.6). This international art fair takes place in Bologna every year. The site-specific installation remained in place for only a few hours on February 4, 2023, and it was curated by Marcello Tedesco.

Yari Miele's research is based on subtle relational links between physical and mental forces, working towards the creation of a new way of thinking and feeling about the city and its spaces. This approach is steered by principles of democracy and inclusivity. Places are conceived to be both physical and mental, designed for the community and its needs. This design aims to encourage and promote relational exchange and dialogue through proximity infrastructures envisioned by artists and professionals. In this way, art ceases to be a niche phenomenon for the elite and embraces the complexity of public life and the city, creating an unprecedented osmosis.

Figure 2.5 Site specific installation by the Italian artist Yari Miele at the biodiversity public garden. Picture by Elettra Giulia Bastoni

Figure 2.6 Activation through the use of a light of the site-specific installation by the Italian artist Yari Miele. Picture by Elettra Giulia Bastoni

Light serves as both the medium and the theme through which Yari Miele orchestrates a complex and captivating interplay of relationships among the work, the environment and the public space. Leveraging reflective fabrics, phosphorescence and fluorescence phenomena, Miele renders visible and tangible the beauty of a world in which all forces are in perfect balance within an incessant and harmonious dynamic. The sculpture in the biodiversity public garden encapsulates the artist's tendency to involve the observer in the creative process, exponentially amplifying the relationship between the artwork and the environment. Suspended between two imposing fir trees, a two-metre-long volume, crafted from aluminium and adorned with a special reflective fabric, comes to life as the public activates it with the torches of their mobile phones.

For just few hours, the public garden was aglow with light, drawing numerous residents, including families with children, and visitors from Arte Fiera. A video reportage of the event was created, documenting the overall engagement at both the CSA headquarters and the public garden during the Art City White Night.

2.2.3 Exhibition “Imagining Public Space with/for Her”

TYPE:	Spot-Place
WHERE:	Onsite - at the biodiversity public garden
WHEN:	20 April - 29 May 2023
WHO:	City Space Architecture network
COMMUNICATION:	emails, telephone, newsletters, social media

Presented within the framework of international initiatives developed by CSA, the exhibition aimed to trigger a crucial debate about public space analysed from a gender perspective. It provided both ideal and physical space to world-wide projects that emphasize the urgency of re-thinking the city and its public spaces with and for women. The intention was to open a specific discussion deeply intertwined with the broader and widely debated challenge of accessibility and inclusiveness of public spaces.

The exhibition unfolded across two distinct venues: the indoor space of CSA headquarters and in the outdoor space of the biodiversity public garden. The indoor exhibition, presented in the form of explanatory panels, featured nine key projects developed by women focusing on gender perspectives in public space. These projects hailed from Italy, Egypt, United Kingdom, Cyprus, Belgium, Kenya, Argentina, and Spain. Encompassing research projects, case studies on cities, exhibitions, reports, and educational activities, the showcase underscored how ensuring the equal participation of women in the design and utilization of public spaces is indispensable for constructing more accessible and inclusive cities for all.

The exhibition in the outdoor space of the biodiversity public garden was brought to life through a series of posters formatted as definitions and quotations, presented as powerful statements (in Italian) to local residents and users (Figures 2.7, 2.8). This way, passers-by were invited to be curious and reflect on those statements as they entered and “inhabited” the garden.

Figure 2.7-2.8. Posters with statements (in Italian) addressing gender issue in public space design displayed at the biodiversity public garden

In May 2023, the city of Bologna invited CSA to showcase the exhibition “Imagining Public Space with/for Her” at an international conference aimed at discussing the outcomes of the first year of the implementation of the Gender Equality Plan, to take place on 11-13 July in Bologna.

The exhibition was held at Palazzo Malvezzi, a Renaissance-style palace located along Via Zamboni in the historic centre, serving as one of the headquarters of the city of Bologna (Figures 2.9, 2.10). The event occurred from 7-13 July 2023. The posters, formerly exhibited at the biodiversity public garden, were assembled into an installation designed to serve as a collection of thoughts and ideas on the redefinition of a gender perspective for public space. Subsequently, the installation was relocated to the biodiversity public garden, where it is currently on display.

Figure 2.9, 2.10. Exhibition at Palazzo Malvezzi, the headquarter of the Metropolitan City of Bologna, during the conference dedicated to the presentation of the Gender Equity Plan, on 7-13 July 2023

2.2.4 Exhibition “European Prize for Urban Public Space”

TYPE:	Spot-Place
WHERE:	Onsite - at the biodiversity public garden
WHEN:	1-30 September 2023
WHO:	City Space Architecture in cooperation with CCCB - Centre of Contemporary Culture of Barcelona, engaging Italian artist Michele Liparesi
COMMUNICATION:	emails, telephone, newsletters, social media

In May 2023, CSA strengthened its ongoing cooperation with the CCCB - Centre of Contemporary Culture of Barcelona with the intention of hosting in Bologna the exhibition of the 2022 edition of the European Prize for Urban Public Space. This biennial competition is organized with the aim of recognizing and showcasing all kinds of works dedicated to creating, recovering, and improving public spaces in European cities. For this purpose, CSA designed and built wooden structures intended to display panels of the 20 selected projects outdoors at the biodiversity public garden (Figures 2.11-2.14). The exhibition also featured the display of the four finalists and the winner indoors at our headquarters. The 25 projects represented a powerful cross-section of public space initiatives across Europe, encompassing both top-down and bottom-up approaches, as well as public and private efforts.

In addition, the outdoor exhibition was enhanced by a work of art by Michele Liparesi - two hanging monkeys in the centre of the garden, creating a playful and joyful environment.

Figure 2.11-2.14. Exhibition of the 2022 edition of the European Prize for Urban Public Space promoted by CCCB at the biodiversity public Garden, with the artwork by Michele Liparesi

The new configuration of the green infrastructure, coupled with the exhibitions and events, clearly showed that what has been an abandoned green space had the potential to become a garden, a welcoming and attractive public space. Unexpectedly, just a few days after completion, residents took the initiative to place two cushions (for young people) and a chair (for older people) at the base of one of the trees, demonstrating their interest in appropriating the space. Later, we put up signs at the entrance to the garden explaining the project, its promoters, and its mission, along with codes of conduct.

In early September, a resident from the building facing the garden generously supported the project by installing a light on her balcony that illuminated the public garden at night, creating a safer environment.

At the beginning of September 2023, the biodiversity public garden hosted two small events:

- A lecture by the Australian artist and educator Fiona Hillary, teaching at the RMIT University in Melbourne, on September 1 (Figure 2.15)
- An open dialogue led by Colombian architect Oscar Perilla who is teaching at Pontificia Universidad Javeriana in Bogotá, on September 6 (Figure 2.16)

Figure 2.15. Lecture by the Australian artist and educator Fiona Hillary, teaching at the RMIT University in Melbourne

Figure 2.16. Open dialogue led by Colombian architect Oscar Perilla teaching at Pontificia Universidad Javeriana in Bogotá

2.3 Reflections

In the fourth year, CSA successfully engaged residents, community members of different ages, cultural backgrounds, and interests, alongside researchers, scholars, local and regional stakeholders, as well as artists and curators, through the activities of “A Resilient Place”. The goal of promoting innovation in knowledge and thinking on urban nature and climate activism was achieved through the involvement of artists and site-specific installations.

Since July 2023, numerous residents and visitors have expressed great appreciation, thanking us for the renovation and ongoing management. They have also posed questions and shown a willingness to help and support the initiative, with some even offering financial contributions. This is particularly important as the garden is not supplied with public water, and CSA is covering the cost of refilling the water tank in the garden through payments to the gardening company responsible for implementing the green infrastructure.

Residents are also expressing concerns about the future of the garden once the cooperation pact with the municipality expires in September 2024. There is a fear that the space could revert to its previous neglected state. This presents a current challenge that CSA has already begun discussing with the municipality, negotiating conditions for an extension of the pact, which would ideally include financial support.

“A Resilient Place” exemplifies how what started as a placemaking intervention to revitalize a derelict space can have a lasting impact. It not only elevates the expectations of local residents but also enhances their eagerness to reclaim the public realm. This process contributes to shaping a sense of ownership and belonging.

3. A Just Radio in Brussels

Rosaura Romero
KU Leuven

3.1 Context

In the fourth year of our journey with "[A Just Radio](#)", we embarked on a series of insightful interviews, both internally with students and faculty members of KU Leuven, and externally with students from various universities in Europe. These conversations were edited, archived, and subsequently shared with our audience on the radio platform known as Rss.com. "A Just Radio" will now transitioned into the capable hands of "Ten Thirty Collective" (1030c), a student collective that emerged from the diverse KU Leuven courses conducted in parallel with the A-Place project based in Brussels over the past four years. This collective can be seen as a direct offshoot of the A-Place project, as it was nurtured by the students who participated in it. Their experiences spurred them to continue developing the critical placemaking practices initiated through a series of placemaking events titled "A Place of Our Own" and "A Just Place."

1030c is an activist group comprised of architecture students, educators, and practitioners who are actively seeking innovative approaches to knowledge exchange. Their mission is to depart from the institutionalized and top-down systems that currently dominate the field of education. Instead, they aim to promote horizontal organizational structures, blurring the boundaries between personal relationships and professional engagements. Their central ethos prioritizes friendship as a driving force for collaboration and exchange, fostering open discussions, evaluations, and the proposal of new methods aligned with the ethics of care and social justice values.

3.2 Activities

During the academic year 2022-23, we initiated a podcast series with the aim of illuminating pressing concerns within architectural education. Our approach involved conducting interviews with a diverse array of focus groups. Our guests consisted of international PhD and Master's students representing a multitude of geographical backgrounds. These students generously shared their insights and participated in thoughtful comparisons, contemplating how the architecture education system could be enhanced and refined.

This endeavor provided us with a deeper comprehension of the challenges currently confronting architectural education, and perhaps even extended to broader issues in higher education. The launch of this podcast series was an integral part of the unveiling of the 1030c.

3.2.1 A Just Radio podcast series recording & editing

TYPE:	Learn-Place
WHERE:	Department of Architecture, KU Leuven, Brussels
WHEN:	October 2022 - May 2023
WHO:	Students, administration, and staff from KU Leuven; pupils from international schools around Europe; guest artists
COMMUNICATION:	Internal to interview invite for each guest and then disseminated on the Rss.com podcast platform https://rss.com/podcasts/collective-1030/

Figures 3.1. A Just Radio recording at KU Leuven Faculty of Architecture

Figures 3.2. A Just Radio recording at KU Leuven Faculty of Architecture

The interview recordings and editing’s started in October 2022, and it extended till May 2023. The series released the 8 episodes at the launch event on May 4th, 2023 (Figures 3.1, 3.2).

3.2.2 1030c website and A Just Radio podcast series launch

TYPE:	Learn-Place
WHERE:	School of Architecture KU Leuven Brussels
WHEN:	May 4, 2023
WHO:	30 Students, administration, and staff from KU Leuven
COMMUNICATION:	Internal invite to all student of the faculty of architecture to join the launch party of website and radio educational series from “A Just Radio”

Figure 3.3. Advertising of the 1030c Website Launch at KU Leuven School of Architecture

Figures 3.4. Architecture students at the Launch event of 1030c collective

During the launch event at the school's cafeteria (Figures 3.3, 3-4), the students had a chance to present the contents of the website and introduced themselves and the groups manuscript.

3.3 Activities

Through "A-Just Radio" we recognized the profound impact of storytelling as an instrument for learning and engagement. In collaboration with 1030c we embarked on an exciting venture into the world of podcasting. We viewed podcasts as an incredibly potent and dynamic medium through which to communicate our thoughts, experiences, and aspirations in a conversational format that deeply resonated with our audience. Our podcast series was carefully crafted to illuminate the multifaceted landscape of architectural education while providing a vibrant platform for diverse voices and critical discourse both within and beyond the A-Place project partnership and the university that hosts us.

These podcast interviews served as a dynamic arena for dialogue, enabling us to delve deeply into critical subjects pertaining to architecture and education. As a result, the interviews emerged as a vivid reflection of the diversity and dynamism inherent to our collective, inviting listeners to join us on our voyage of discovery and exploration.

We believe it is important to keep providing a dedicated space for underrepresented topics and perspectives, which is why we acknowledge the necessity to pass along the baton to a group that would evolve and continue beyond the context of the A-Place project. We aspire to further advance inclusivity and diversity both within and outside the Department of Architecture in KU Leuven Brussels. The idea of a collective transcending the project allows for our efforts within the project to keep evolving.

4. AGORA - APlace4All

Veronika Antoniou, Teresa Tourvas
Urban Gorillas, Nicosia

4.1 Context

AGORA, designed by Urban Gorillas in 2023, is a mobile structure that functions as a versatile platform for a range of events. Easily assembled and adaptable to various scenarios, its primary objective is to enliven spaces and promote community engagement through arts and participatory activities that enrich democracy. The structure, composed of 600 pieces and 180 joints, can be configured in various formats, acting as a cultural driver to host diverse activities in different spaces.

4.2 Activities

In 2023, Urban Gorillas (UG) initiated a series of events using the AGORA as a cultural and social catalyst. It was activated in two significant events:

- At the Afrobanana Festival with the activity "A Silent Place in the AGORA", hosting artists Orancosang from Japan and their performative art piece Hitsudankai.
- At Pame Kaimakli Festival, it functioned as "AGORA-APlace4All", serving as the central focal point of the festival (see Deliverable 3.6.1). It hosted festival facilities such as pop-up cinema, workshops, theatre stage, info point and lounge.

Presently, discussions are underway for its potential adoption by the Larnaca municipality as part of the European Capital of Culture programme, ensuring that its role as a cultural beacon continues to expand and evolve.

4.2.1 A Just Expo

TYPE:	Spot-Place
WHERE:	Performative art, community engagement
WHEN:	14 July 2023
WHO:	Urban Gorillas, Orancosong, ARB alternative minds.
COMMUNICATION:	social media, local press, radio

The Afrobanana Festival is a vibrant four-day music event attracting throngs of young attendees and boasting a lineup of world-class musicians from across the globe. UG were invited to instal the AGORA at the festival, as a place of silence and reflexion of festival-goers (Figures 4.1-4.3). It also provided a platform for a performance and workshop of two Japanese artists from Orancosong, featuring their unique performance, Hitsudankai. This silent and participatory performance stood as a stark contrast to the festival's bustling soundscape, delving into alternative communication methods and engaging festival attendees in a silent yet playful message exchange.

The structure was thoughtfully designed, considering the methodology of the Orancosong performance. It transformed into a dynamic space during the event, featuring a sizable table and a roll of paper that unfurled to display the outcomes of the performance.

This initiative received generous support from the Commonwealth Foundation, A-Place, JEC Osaka World Commemorative Fund, and the Embassy of Japan in Cyprus.

Figures 4.1-4.3. A silent place at Afrobanana festival

4.2.2 A Place 4 All: Pame Kaimakli, Istories allosFos

TYPE:	Spot-Place
WHERE:	Diverse art forms
WHEN:	1-23 September 2023
WHO:	Urban Gorillas, Kaimakli neighbours, Students and volunteers (locals and migrants)
COMMUNICATION:	Open call for festival participation; local media channels; newspapers, radio, social media channels. Invitation to help in the assembly through local social media networks

In 2023, the Pame Kaimakli festival celebrated its 10th anniversary with the theme "Istories allosFos," translated as "Stories through a Different Light." This year's festival centred around the art of storytelling, revealing previously hidden truths and showcasing unseen neighbourhood protagonists. The festival aimed to provide a fresh perspective on historical narratives and places, unveiling new possibilities in an engaging manner.

The heart of the festival was marked by the installation of a versatile temporary structure named "AGORA-APlace4All" (Figure 4.4). Positioned prominently in the central square and spanning approximately 120m², this structure served as the hub of the festival activities. Not only did it energize the central square, but it also accommodated workshops, a pop-up cinema, theatrical performances, artist installations, and a curated talk. It also provided a comfortable lounge for attendees. Beyond the festival's agenda, the structure also hosted activities from other two other Creative Europe programmes, specifically EMPACT and ECRN.

While many artists who leveraged this unique space were funded by the Pame Kaimakli festival, the activities directly associated with A-Place included:

1. **Reception Desk & Information Space:** Attendees could gather details about the festival and learn more about the A-Place project. The information about the A-Place pop-up cinema was also available within the structure's premises.
2. **Bi-Communal Children's Event:** Children aged 5-11 from both Turkish Cypriot and Greek Cypriot communities came together in Kaimakli for a unique herbal aroma workshop. This workshop combined a brief tour of Kaimakli's gardens, where children collected herbs and learned about their medicinal properties. They then crafted herbal aromas. This initiative was backed by the Commonwealth Foundation and the UNFICYP (UN peacemaking forces of Cyprus).
3. **Stencil Workshops & Mural Creation:** Aimed at youth (aged 16+) and Kaimakli residents, these workshops culminated in a community-driven mural. The mural's design centred on promoting social and environmental sustainability through themes of empathy and inclusivity. Orchestrated under the EMPACT - Creative Europe programme, this project saw a collaboration between architect Konstantinos Avramidis and street artist Twenty-Three.
4. **Artistic Talks:** Artists Larsen Bervorst and UG member Marina Kyriakou delivered a presentation discussing the Creative Europe Program ECRN, which focuses on transforming rooftops through artistic interventions.
5. **A-Place Pop-Up Cinema & Lounge:** Throughout the Pame Kaimakli festival, AGORA served as a cinematic venue (Figures 4.5, 4.6), showcasing various screenings and theatrical performances (details available in Deliverable 3.6.1)

Figure 4.4. Invitations of events which took place in the AGORA-APlace4All

Figures 4.5, 4.6. The structure in use during the Pame Kaimakli festival 2023

4.3 Reflections

AGORA provided an invaluable platform for experimenting with diverse configurations and capabilities in the design and setup of this mobile structure. This initiative has opened avenues for collaborative design, wherein residents and users actively participated in shaping the structure to their needs and visions.

Its presence in public spaces and events has magnetically drawn individuals who typically wouldn't engage in such collaborative endeavours, amplifying the community spirit within the Kaimakli neighbourhood (Figure 4.7). Notably, during its installation in both instances, pedestrians spontaneously volunteered to assist and immerse themselves in the process, truly becoming an integral part of the project.

The versatility of the structure, demonstrated by its ability to rejuvenate spaces and cater to an ever-evolving user base, paints a promising picture for its future. Its adaptability and the forthcoming endeavours under the cultural capital programme are brimming with potential. We are optimistic about its continued evolution, not just as a physical entity, but as a dynamic cultural hub that can adapt, inspire, and transform.

Figure 4.7. Passersby took photographs and used the structure as a resting point during a cycling tour of Nicosia

Conclusions

With this report we conclude the series of yearly accounts of the placemaking activities carried out by partners in local communities.

In its inaugural year (2019-20), the A-Place project was significantly influenced by the unforeseen Covid-19 pandemic, shaping the exploration of place and placemaking. "[A Weaved Place](#)" in L'Hospitalet started not in the city but in the digital space, and a music concert planned in the Lisbon Mouraria neighbourhood in "[A Sound Place](#)" was streamed. Faced with impossibilities in accessing physical spaces, we proactively ventured into digital territories to uncover emerging sensitivities towards place that emerged globally during this unique period. "[A Confined Place](#)" was our creative response to the imposed constraints.

Some activities in public spaces could start as the lockdown restrictions ceased, as the rediscovery of "[A Calm Place](#)" in the Schaerbeek district in Brussels. In the following year (2020-21), the activities shifted their focus towards physical territories while concurrently continuing exploration in digital environments. We created the "[A-Place: MAPPING](#)" tool to collect experiences of places worldwide and initiated the "[A Seedling Place](#)" programme, which seamlessly combined physical experiences in multiple locations and contexts with the capacity of digital tools to foster community creation. In addition, we delved into local territories, implementing a series of projects integrated into sociophysical environments: "[A Weaved Place](#)," "[A Happy Place](#)," "[A Pla\(y\)ce](#)," and "[A Visionary Place](#)" unfolded in outdoor spaces, and "[A Place of our Own](#)" indoors. Finally, we started the development of a "[Glossary](#)" on the website to systematize placemaking experiences conducted by partners across diverse locations, involving various stakeholders and employing multiple art forms.

The work conducted in the second year provided a guiding direction for the third one (2021-22). Partners strengthened community relationships through educational and creative activities. In "[A Weaved Place](#)", architecture students and pupils from local schools re-signified the public space with objects and installations collaboratively designed and built. The activities focusing on Lisbon neighbourhoods continued with a new programme, "[A Reconnecting Place](#)" in Bairro do Rego; "[A Happy Place](#)" concluded the physical transformation of a Brussels playground in the Dardaar district while the premises of the Grand Hospice in Brussels became the operations base of "[A Just Place](#)"; and "[A Re-place](#)" continued with activities in the Krater area, in Ljubljana. Towards the end of the year, partners carried out some joint activities in Brussels: creating a [map visualizing connections](#) between the partner activities, reflecting on the glossary terms at [Grand Hospice chapel](#), and participating in the final activities and opening ceremony of "[A Happy Place](#)" in Dardaar.

The fourth and last year has been marked by the preparation of the closing events and final travelling exhibition (see [Deliverable 3.7](#)). This has left less space than in previous years for the local activities. Nevertheless, "[A Weaved Place](#)" concluded the four-year collaboration with the communities of L'Hospitalet with the open art festival "[ES CULTURA](#)"; "[A Resilient Place](#)" completed the transformation of a derelict green spot in Bologna; "[A Just Radio](#)" continued with the public debates on design justice using podcasts; and a mobile and mountable structure was installed at two events in Nicosia creating an "[AGORA-APlace4All](#)".

Throughout the entire project, teachers and students from diverse educational levels, artists representing various disciplines, and residents from different backgrounds, played pivotal roles in creating places across various cities. Musicians, composers, dancers, filmmakers and multidisciplinary artists, contributed to a diverse array of creations which added new values and meanings to public spaces. New learning places, emerging at the intersection of academia and community, were embedded in public spaces and communities, engaging students, faculty, and artists in their conception and implementation.

Throughout the project's development, a cross-fertilization of the diverse strategies, methods and techniques employed by partners at their placemaking activities became evident. This intermingling of approaches not only unfolded in the processes but also manifested in several of the outputs produced. The diversity of placemaking activities across different cities and locations enriched the overall project with a multiplicity of creative and community engaging activities. Furthermore, the impact of this intertwining extended to the outputs, whether in the form of artistic creations or tangible transformation in public spaces. Some of the interventions in different places carry the imprint of a -deliberate or inadvertent- collaborative exchange, highlighting the importance of A-Place as a space to foster a multifaceted approach to placemaking.